

Distributed but Integrated: Forming a Science Gateway from Multiple Parts

Holger Gauza, Steve Kaminski, Jens Krüger*, Fabian Paz,
Halima Saker, Fabian Wannemacher, Johannes Werner, Thomas Zajac
High Performance and Cloud Computing Group at IT Center
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen
*jens.krueger@uni-tuebingen.de

Olaf Brandt, Jan Kaltenbach
University Library
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen

Abstract—Science gateways represent a framework to implement, integrate, and provide service to a scientific user community. But often additional requirements have to be met and other tools have to be used to implement and link e.g. data publishing, search, and metadata annotation. Instead of integrating every necessary function or tool into a monolithic science gateway, the Science Data Center BioDATEN (<https://portal.biodaten.info/>) experiments with a lateral approach. A HUBzero-based science gateway is implemented in parallel to other components such as InvenioRDM for data publishing, VuFind for data search, and a homebrew tool to annotate metadata. These components are connected by a single sign-on infrastructure that offers seamless user integration. This topology in combination with the tools and services implemented helps to make research data FAIR data while reducing effort and enhancing usability. These services are implemented on de.NBI Cloud infrastructure adding extra reliability and sustainability to research data management.

Keywords—BioDATEN, science gateway, lateral integration, data publishing, distributed tools, FAIR data, research data management, cloud infrastructure, Keycloak

I. INTRODUCTION

Science gateways play an important role in providing the scientific community with tools, workflows, and the general means for good research. In recent times, not only good research is gaining importance but also good research data management. Most notably, this is expressed by the FAIR data principles that require research data to be Findable, Accessable, Interoperable, and Reuseable [1]. To accommodate for those requirements, tools and services supporting the scientific community in making their data FAIR have to be integrated into the scientific workflows and thus also in science gateways. As the integration of several external tools and services into a science gateway would most likely pose a significant burden in programming and maintaining, the Science Data Center BioDATEN (<https://portal.biodaten.info/>) is experimenting with the lateral integration of services that are governed by a common log-in infrastructure. In this topology, tools and services are implemented in parallel and a science gateway serves as a facade that provides seamless integration. The benefit of this approach is reduced effort while providing full functionality to the scientific community. Especially for services requiring long term preservation of research data sets, a decoupling and only loose integration can provide considerable advantages on the operational side. This paper

starts with a description of the BioDATEN scientific community and its requirements in Section III which is followed by the description and motivation of a lateral topology in Section IV. The governing component Keycloak is described in Section V. The work focusing on metadata curation and dataset publishing is addressed in sections VI and VII.

II. RELATED WORK

As phrased by Wilkinson et.al. FAIR stands for findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability [1]. They identified a several shortcomings in the scientific life cycle of scholarly articles, hindering scientific progression. The focus on the researcher prevents the unhindered view on the research data itself. They proclaim to establish suitable infrastructures to facilitate the (automated) usage of research data. The idea and spirit were much appreciated and triggered a boost for modern research data management in all scientific communities. Consequently, a funding program for Science Data Centres was set up by the state of Baden-Württemberg, offering the chance for chemists (MoMaf), economists (BERD), literary studies (SDC4Lit), and life scientists (BioDATEN) to improve the data management infrastructure for their communities.

Hubzero is a software framework facilitating the creation of science gateways and community portals [2]. It was originally developed at Purdue University and is now maintained by the Sustainable Scientific Software Group at the San Diego Supercomputer Center. The framework builds on open-source technologies e.g., Joomla for content management in conjunction with PHP web scripting. Customised installations can offer a broad range of functionality, covering collaboration tools, data sharing and simulation tools.

InvenioRDM [3] is an open-source research data management repository application which is primarily developed at CERN and Northwestern University together with several other partners. InvenioRDM is described by its developers at CERN as a turn-key research data management repository and its features are tailored to the collection and storage of research data formats and sizes of all kinds. The repository is highly scalable up to millions of data records and has already proven itself in productive use in Invenio variants such as ZENODO [4]. Its basic aim is to foster research data preservation and reusability. InvenioRDM plays an important role in the research

data publication process as it is the component that registers DOIs and as such makes research data accessible and citeable.

VuFind [6] is an open-source search portal, mainly designed for libraries and textual resources which are developed and maintained by Villanova University Library and other stakeholders all over the world. The basic search engine is SOLR [7]. VuFind provides facet-based search functionalities. Usually, it is based in conjunction with a standard MARC21-metadata schema, yet it is highly flexible and adaptable. One of the BioDATEN project partners, the Tübingen University Library has broad experience in configuring, extending and maintaining VuFind for different purposes, especially for special subject collections and bibliographies.

III. BIODATEN COMMUNITY

As mentioned earlier, there are four Science Data Centers (SDC) sponsored by the Ministry for Science, Research, and Art of the federal state of Baden-Württemberg in Germany. Each SDC targets a specific community to develop and foster research data management techniques. The BioDATEN scientific community consists of researchers in various heterogeneous fields of biology. Their research includes diverse technologies, such as metagenomics and metaproteomics analysis of livestock, single-cell omics, cancer research, fundamental plant research on moss and fern, degenerative neurological diseases, and developmental biology. They all do research in life sciences and all work on various omics data sets. This broad range of research areas was chosen on purpose when conceptualising BioDATEN to generate as much diverse input from the community as possible. This results in very high demands on the metadata annotation and schemata but also offers the chance to provide solutions for common needs. All life scientists in Baden-Württemberg, and of course beyond, are in need for resilient solutions to store, share and publish their research data. They need efficient ways to annotate their data in a transparent way, finding a balance between specificity and adaptability. The resulting well-annotated data sets need to be searchable offering the chance to cross-link information to offer the chance for additional insight. Consequently, the wish for data publication employing unique, citable identifiers is a common need among the individual communities.

IV. LATERAL SCIENCE GATEWAY TOPOLOGY

The term *lateral integration* is commonly used as an economic term and describes the merger of different companies under common management that is not direct competitors but is still producing related products. The result is usually a diversified company with risks spread across different markets or enhanced revenue. Transferring this concept to research data management and science gateways results in the following analogy:

- Related product = Work in research data management or community services
- Different markets = Tools and services with different scopes or functions
- Reduced risk = Less programming needed, upstream compatibility
- Enhanced revenue = Greater usability for users

In case of the SDC BioDATEN, this results in a topology in which multiple stand-alone tools and services - each with its own *raison d'être* - are implemented in parallel and are connected by a governing log-in infrastructure that allows for seamless access to all tools and services. In our case, the HUBzero-based science gateway is the facade for other services like InvenioRDM, VuFind, etc. while the main connection between those services is done by the authorisation infrastructure Keycloak. Coming back to the analogy, the advantages are simple: As the tools and services are implemented in parallel, there is no need for tight integration into the science gateway or even a re-implementation. Thus, the risk is reduced by avoiding programming and implementation efforts, by saving time, and by being upstream compatible regarding security patches and functions. At the same time, users have access and are able to use tools and services in their plain state. This results in the same usability or functional range as the tool or service without the science gateway. The overall envisioned topology is displayed in Figure 1. In essence, the approach of lateral service integration provides benefits for infrastructure providers and the scientific community as well. Infrastructure providers such as Science Data Centers, university computing centers, e-science facilities, or core facilities benefit from reduced implementation effort, upstream compatibility, and time-saving. The scientific community benefits from faster deployment and plain state functionality of services and tools. In the following section, the purpose of the different tools and services is shortly described.

HUBzero The HUBzero-based science gateway is the central entry point to BioDATEN tools and services [8]. In this function, the science gateway has multiple roles. For external presentation, HUBzero provides the CMS to produce the project's homepage. After log-in, registered users have access to cloud resources by the integration of a plug-in that connects to de.NBI Cloud storage, see also section VIII for details about de.NBI Cloud. HUBzero serves as a facade for the scientific community as it bundles internal and lateral implemented tools and services. Thus, the main function of a science gateway is limitlessly available.

Metadata annotation and curation tool Metadata are crucial for FAIR research data as they make data sets searchable and interoperable. Especially for BioDATEN the demanding heterogeneous requirements from multiple (sub-)communities pose a challenge. More details are provided in section VI.

VuFind Although the main focus of VuFind is textual resources in the library context, its underlying mechanics are highly flexible and allow us besides a full text-based search a facet-based search on metadata. Besides that, there are other key features, that ease the integration in the BioDATEN-

Fig. 1. Lateral arranged components governed by log-in infrastructure.

context. The developed metadata schema in combination with the metadata annotation and curation tool will serve as input for the search engine. In this way, the scientific community will be offered search functionalities that go well beyond simple full-text search and are based on more structured metadata, see Figure 3 for a demo display.

InvenioRDM A key concept of FAIR research data is the accessibility and citability of data sets. Here, research data repositories such as InvenioRDM play an important role, see Section VII for more details. The basic idea is that repositories provide public access to research data but are also able to enact retention periods if researchers wish or are obliged to do so. They also implement mechanics to register persistent identifiers such as DOIs to ensure the citability of data sets. Currently, the metadata used for DOI registration focus on descriptive metadata such as author, creator, and related publications. These metadata are also annotated by the metadata annotation and curation tool.

The tacit assumption is that the services described above can exchange data with each other via APIs or similar means instead of implementing a central data management. Each component produces (meta)data that are either used by downstream components or used by the component itself. For example, the metadata annotation and curation tool produce rich metadata that are in part or in a reduced form used by InvenioRDM to publish data and for DOI registration. These data are exchanged by using a REST-API. Note, metadata covering, e.g., sample preparation are not needed for DOI registration and are thus not exposed to InvenioRDM. Simultaneously, the rich metadata are exposed to VuFind to realise a faceted search index. The combination and lateral integration of the services described above enable us to provide a modern data management environment following the FAIR data principles [1] by using communicating, specialized, and dedicated tools.

No matter how well services are programmed and maintained they need a sound hardware environment to be installed on and reliable storage to ensure data availability for more than just the project duration. The services already described as well as potentially other services rely on the de.NBI Cloud infrastructure, see section VIII for further details.

V. KEYCLOAK-BASED SINGLE SIGN-ON

Keycloak is an open source identity and access management solution enabling the integration of diverse services with existing identity providers [9]. Authentication and authorisation are

supported through the OAuth 2, OpenID Connect and SAML 2.0 protocols, allowing for integration with a heterogeneous landscape of services. Placed centrally between those services on the one hand side and identity providers on the other, Keycloak functions as a single sign-on (SSO) provider, enhancing identity providers (IDPs) lacking this functionality.

A central organisational concept in Keycloak are realms, representing a grouping of services that can be accessed through defined identity providers by a common user base. Adding authentication and authorisation capabilities to a new service can thus be achieved by setting up a realm client for one of the aforementioned protocols. The existing user base is then able to use their preferred identity provider e.g. from their home university to log-in to the new service.

While Keycloak allows to integrate with multiple IDPs and has some functionality to automatically merge corresponding identities, the BioDATEN Keycloak interfaces with Elixir AAI, which itself is an authorisation and authentication infrastructure for academic institutions in Europe [10]. For mid 2022 a migration and transition to the Life Science Research Infrastructure is anticipated which will cover all of the ELIXIR AAI functionality [11].

Integrating Elixir AAI as an IDP allows authentication for all institutions participating in eduGAIN (EDUCation Global Authentication INFRAstructure) and for third parties through ORCID, Google or LinkedIn. All supported user identities can be merged and attached to the Elixir ID, a globally unique, unchanging identifier and primary source of identity in Elixir AAI. This effectively means taking advantage of already merged identities and only dealing with a unified identity in Keycloak and the attached services.

While relying on an established infrastructure for authentication, employing Keycloak as part of our infrastructure allows for more flexibility with regard to authorisation. Fine grained access controls can be defined based on roles, attributes or custom logic derived from either. This makes it possible to handle different requirements across services and only expose necessary information. Although Keycloak provides the technical means described above, a mapping between different 3rd-party systems has to be done and specialized workflows might be necessary to reflect, e.g., requirements regarding DOI registration to prevent misuse and ensure data quality. In essence, Keycloak serves as common link between services, giving service providers control over SSO and authorisation aspects.

VI. METADATA ANNOTATION AND CURATION

The collection of metadata often takes place at a late stage in the data management process and represents an undesirable additional work for researchers, as often detailed information from the past is required to be reconstructed in a time-consuming way. Therefore, we developed a framework for automatic metadata generation which can be enriched by the researcher throughout the data life cycle. For this purpose, we automatically create a complex and extensible metadata scaffold (see Figure 1) including technical metadata (file size,

file type, etc.) as well as users' information for every research data record uploaded via the gateway.

The direct creation and editing of complex XML based metadata documents by the researcher is generally not reasonable and makes a supporting set of tools necessary. Therefore, we developed a metadata annotation tool based on an XSLT processor using XSD2HTML2XML to convert XML schema definitions into human readable web forms [12]. The XSLT processor is embedded in a metadata workflow of generating editable forms from the schema, followed by the conversion into XML-based metadata records and their subsequent storage in suitable database systems (XML-enabled Postgresql). Since metadata records can be very extensive in terms of information, our framework allows incomplete information to be stored in the database at any time as an interim status and to be completed at a later point in time. Technically, a continuous back-and-forth conversion between an XML-based dataset and a corresponding web form can take place until the researcher has provided a complete set of information describing the research data. Our tool also provides the researcher with information about the status of their data, especially with regard to whether all metadata are sufficiently available for a publication. A key feature is the connection to the Keycloak authorisation and authentication service that allows users a login and access to their metadata using their home institution's credentials via Shibboleth, Elixir ID or other IDPs.

To ensure a high quality of metadata, subject-specific vocabularies are assigned to some input fields in the web form, which provide input options either by drop-down or by auto-complete feature. All identifier information is saved here so that the full context can always be restored.

In order to enable the most flexible and at the same time standardised annotation of research data, we decided to use the XML-based container format METS [13]. METS is maintained by the standards office of the American Library of Congress and is considered to be a suitable container format for metadata. METS has been shown to be sufficiently flexible and interoperable for the integration of other XML-based schemas to represent descriptive, administrative as well as community-specific metadata for research data objects and to enable data exchange via standardised and widely supported protocols such as OAI-PMH [14]. Especially the combination of METS and PREMIS [15] is to be regarded as a *de facto* standard and a wide range of requirements for the annotation of research data can be implemented with it.

Our complete metadata scaffold consists of four different sections embedded in a METS container (see Figure 2). Here, descriptive metadata (upper left corner) using the DataCite format is mainly provided manually by the researcher supported via our annotation tool. PREMIS metadata (lower right corner) stores technical file information as well as provenance data, automatically captured through our framework. To account for data records generated from high performance computing jobs, we include job feedback information as automatically provided by workload managers like SLURM [16] and MOAB

[17]. These information are automatically mapped (lower left corner) to the XML based LML standard (Large-scale System Markup Language) [18] developed at the Jülich Supercomputing Center. The last quadrant (upper right corner) of the metadata framework is an entirely flexible one, reserved for community specific information. Here, the researcher needs to choose from available and curated schema to incorporate with the help of our in-house annotation tool.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the metadata framework based on four segments. The red rectangles denote the type of metadata, the blue ovals the specific schema in use and the grey rectangles describe the source of metadata information. The overall schema is encapsulated in a container format based on METS.

VII. DATASET PUBLISHING

Maintaining research data and keeping them findable as well as accessible over time according to the FAIR principles requires at least two things: First, the technical platform that ensures functional access to the data. Second, persistent identification of data sets. More ideally, the scope of persistent identification is widened to authors and institutions alike. As mentioned previously in this paper, BioDATEN as well as other projects in research data management, e.g. DataPLANT [19], opted for InvenioRDM as a technical platform to make data sets accessible. Persistent identification of data sets will be handled by integrating the DOI registration via our local DataCite consortium in InvenioRDM [20]. Just before publishing data sets in the repository, the registration process will be started which relies on metadata that have been collected during the metadata annotation process.

A particular challenge is the persistent identification of persons associated with the data set to be published. Means of identification like institutional email addresses and IDs that are tied to a person's employment status at a research institution or simply names have been proven to be not sufficient. Researchers tend to change their research institutions and thus loose institutional mail addresses or simply marry and thus change their name. Here, the use of ORCID [21] and the collection of the researchers' ORCID during the metadata annotation and curation process has been envisioned by BioDATEN. ORCID allows researchers to manage and take care of their own profiles while providing persistent IDs that can be referenced.

Fig. 3. Excerpt from the search platform VuFind. Using VuFind, researchers can conveniently search through data collections via both free-text and facet-based methods. Only dummy data sets are shown here.

The publication of data sets is considered to mark the end of the research data lifecycle. But by publishing well annotated and citable research data, these data can be used by other researchers to start a new research data life cycle.

VIII. RESILIENT INFRASTRUCTURE: DE.NBI CLOUD

The academic and non-profit de.NBI (German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure) Cloud is a cloud federation at separate locations (Berlin, Bielefeld, Gießen, Freiburg, Heidelberg, Tübingen) which provides both computation and storage resources for scientific research projects nationwide. BioDATEN is relying on the compute and storage resources of the de.NBI Cloud in Tübingen. Universities, research institutes and academic institutions in Germany can apply for these resources and access them after approval in order to analyse their research data. For that, they need to authenticate via the ELIXIR AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure), which allows users to connect to the cloud with the same credentials they use for their academic origin organisations. The cloud resource management is organised via OpenStack which allows to deploy and manage tailored virtual machines (VMs) for different application scenarios. As both research focus and requirements are different between diverse cloud projects, the hardware resources of each VM are organised in flavors that are designed for different requirements. These flavors define the available virtualised resources, such as computer cores, memory and disk space. Furthermore, a selection of different, in some cases hardened, operating systems are provided, which can also be extended in special cases. Internally, strict network configurations are applied in the cloud infrastructure. Tools are provided for cloud users to easily configure firewalls and add networks enabled for them. Access to a VM is exclusively possible with the user’s own SSH keys. These security measures contribute significantly to the protection against foreign access. Carefully managed storage systems also enable separate management of stored data and computing environments, which means that

Fig. 4. General overview of the de.NBI Cloud infrastructure in Tübingen.

multiple secure infrastructures can be operated, allowing the processing of sensitive data in a GDPR compliant way. To be able to fulfil the need of all the distributed components of the BioDATEN portal, the de.NBI Cloud provides redundant storage that is accessible seamlessly via several interfaces like S3 and POSIX-Filesystems. This allows different components to access data in the way needed and renders additional copies to different storage types that have to be kept in sync superfluous. As an example, this gives the possibility to analyse the data with fast random file reads to add metadata from one component while another component provides the same data via http accessible S3-Object for downloads to external sites. As part of the continuous improvement and maintenance of the information security aspects of the de.NBI Cloud, efforts have been made in recent years to have the individual sites certified to ISO 27001. This ISO standard essentially demands the operation of an information security management system and thus represents verifiable proof, not only of a certain level of information security but also of the ongoing improvement and addressing of the same. The de.NBI Cloud site in Tübingen used for the BioDATEN project is characterised by geo-redundant server locations in Tübingen and solid experience in processing and storing sensitive data, as well as the availability of GPU servers with high computing power. Geo-redundancy in particular provides projects with a considerable degree of data resilience. Close contact with support personnel also enables efficient and transparent work with the cloud.

IX. CONCLUSION

The current approach of lateral service integration provides the SDC BioDATEN with enough flexibility to tackle the

tasks on route to FAIR data without the need for the development of tightly integrated plug-ins. Necessary services are implemented in parallel and governed by a common log-in infrastructure which in combination with a HUBzero-based science gateway provides a sufficient degree of integration. The services described in this paper and their interplay fulfil requirements posed by the FAIR principles. Research data are annotated with metadata using a homebrew metadata annotation tool aiming at making them searchable. Searchability is realised by the flexible VuFind search engine using full text and facet search. InvenioRDM is used to publish research data and for DOI registration. All these services reside on the resilient infrastructure of the de.NBI Cloud Tübingen. This hardware environment adds reliability and sustainability to the BioDATEN services and tools. Lateral service integration governed by a common log-in infrastructure facilitates FAIR research data handling while reducing programming efforts for maintainers and enhancing usability for the scientific community.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The SDC BioDATEN is supported by the Ministry for Science, Research, Arts of the federal state Baden-Württemberg. We acknowledge support for DataPLANT through the German National Research Data Initiative (442077441). The authors also acknowledge the use of the de.NBI Cloud and the support by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) through grant no 031A535A and the state of Baden-Württemberg through bwHPC and the German Research Foundation (DFG) through grant no INST 37/935-1 FUGG.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I. Aalbersberg, et al. *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*. Scientific Data 3, 160018, 2016, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18
- [2] M. McLennan and R Kennel, *HUBzero: A Platform for Dissemination and Collaboration in Computational Science and Engineering*, Computing in Science & Engineering, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 48-53, 2010, doi: 10.1109/MCSE.2010.41.
- [3] *InvenioRDM - The turn-key research data management repository* <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>. (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [4] *Zenodo - Research. Shared.* <https://zenodo.org/>. (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [5] Belmann P, Fischer B, Krüger J, et al. *de.NBI Cloud federation through ELIXIR AAI*. F1000Res. 2019;8:842. Published 2019 Jun 10. doi:10.12688/f1000research.19013.1
- [6] *VuFind - Search. Discover. Share.* <https://vufind.org/>. (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [7] *Apache Solr.* <https://solr.apache.org/>. (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [8] *BioDATEN Portal* <https://portal.biodaten.info>. (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [9] *Keycloak* <https://www.keycloak.org> (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [10] Linden, M., Prochazka, M., Lappalainen, I., Bucik, D., Vyskocil, P., Kuba, M., Silén, S., Belmann, P., Sczyrba, A., Newhouse, S., Matyska, L., & Nyrönen, T. (2018). *Common ELIXIR Service for Researcher Authentication and Authorisation*. F1000Research, 7, ELIXIR-1199. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.15161.1>
- [11] *Life Science Research Infrastructure* <https://lifescience-ri.eu/login/elixir-migration-news.html/> (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [12] *XSD2HTML2XML* <https://github.com/MichielCM/xsd2html2xml> (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [13] L. Cantara, *METS: The metadata encoding and transmission standard*. Cataloging & classification quarterly, 40(3-4):237-253,2005.
- [14] Herbert Van de Sompel, et al. *Resource harvesting within the OAI-PMH framework* D-lib magazine, 10(12), 2004.

- [15] *PREservation Metadata Implementation Strategies.* <https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis> (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [16] *SLURM: Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management* https://slurm.schedmd.com/slurm_design.pdf (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [17] *MOAB HPC Suite* <https://adaptivecomputing.com/moab-hpc-suite/> (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [18] *LML: Large-scale System Markup Language.* <http://llview.fz-juelich.de/LML/OnlineDocumentation/lmldoc.html> (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [19] *DataPLANT.* <https://nfidi4plants.de> (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [20] *DataCITE.* <https://datacite.org>. (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)
- [21] *ORCID. Connecting research and researchers.* <https://orcid.org> (Accessed: 18-Mar-2022)